

Mechanical Modeling on the Phase Morphology of Blends of a Thermosetting Aryl Dicyanate Resin with Thermoplastic Polymers

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ABSTRACT

As the thermoplastic contents in the dicyanate/polymer blend system were increased (20 vol% and above), a notable change in the phase composition and morphology was observed in the dispersed domains and a continuous thermoplastic phase started to form while the thermosetting dicyanate continuous phase retreated rapidly. A proposed mechanical model was successfully used to describe the dynamic mechanical modulus data. The modeling results suggested interesting shifts in the phase continuity of the blends as a function of the thermoplastic contents. The findings from the modeling were also further experimentally substantiated by additional results of studies on a polyetherimide (PEI)-modified epoxy system.

INTRODUCTION

Aromatic cyanate resins such as bisphenol-E dicyanate (BEDCy) are attracting increasing interest. They can crosslink to form polycyanates by forming very thermally stable cyclic triazine rings, which resemble cyclic ester rings except that the oxygen atom is now a nitrogen atom. Polycyanates possess low dielectric constants and high thermal stabilities [1]. The cured dicyanates, or polycyanates, all possess high glass transition temperatures (250 - 280 °C), low water sorption, and excellent processability and compatibility with carbon fibers [2]. Recent studies have focused on their potential matrix applications in advanced composites. [3-10] Control and prediction of phase morphology of the

thermoplastic-modified polycyanates become quite complex. Continuity of the phase domains comprising of the thermoplastic and the thermosetting components has been found to significantly influence the fracture toughness, solvent resistance, and other properties of the thermoplastic-modified polycyanates [11]. We have reported earlier interesting results in thermoplastic-modified bisphenol-E dicyanate resins, where the morphology and its correlation with properties was well described by a novel mechanical model [11,12]. This study further attempted to experimentally confirmed this model of correlation by demonstrating on a cured network formed by an epoxy blend with thermoplastic polymers.

EXPERIMENTAL

The dicyanate resin used in this study was of a low-viscosity liquid form (bisphenol-A dicyanate (BEDCy)) obtained from Rhone Poulenc, Inc. (U.S.A. Division), and two amorphous thermoplastic polymers were used to blend with the dicyanate resin. The thermoplastic polymers were polysulfone (Amoco UDEL^R P1700) with a T_g of 185 °C and polyetherimide (GE Ultem 1000) with a T_g of 210 °C. They were also both used as received. The PEI has $M_n = 12,000$ and $M_w = 30,000$. A melt mixing technique was used to prepare samples of relatively low thermoplastic contents (20 wt% or less). A catalyst, which as supplied is a 20:1 mixture of nonylphenol with copper acetylacetonate, was used at about 2 wt% of the resin mixture. After mixing, the resin mixtures were poured into a glass mold which had been treated with a mold release agent. Cure reactions were performed for the thermoplastic/dicyanate mixtures by heating to 177 °C with an isothermal hold for two hours at that temperature, followed with a postcure at 220 °C for two hours.

Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) was performed by using a DuPont DMA-983 in a flexural bending mode. The storage and loss moduli were recorded automatically by a DuPont TA-2000 system for data acquisition and analysis. A heating rate of 5 °C/min and a fixed frequency of 1 Hz were used. A differential scanning calorimeter (Perkin-Elmer DSC-7) was used for measuring residual heat of reactions and to observe the glass transition temperature of the blends. The morphology of the thermoplastic-modified polycyanate samples was studied by using optical and electron microscopy techniques. The morphology of the cured resins as well as blends of various cure extents was examined using a scanning electron microscope (SEM) (JEOL, two models, JSM-35 or JXA-840, were used). The fractured samples were coated with gold by vapor deposition using a vacuum sputterer. Some of the fractured samples were etched with solvent (methylene chloride) before they were sputter-coated and examined using SEM.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The DSC results indicated that the binary blends of the thermoplastic with BEDCy dicyanate resin were miscible at all compositions before cure of the thermosetting component. However, after full cure, the clear dicyanate/thermoplastic mixtures turned into a crosslinked thermoplastic-thermoset network with a cloudy appearance. Phase heterogeneity was apparently observed for all cured thermoplastic-modified dicyanate blends of all compositions, as evidenced by the DSC and DMA results revealing two T_g 's. In order to describe the morphology changes as the thermoplastic contents were varied in the polycyanate networks, simple models consisting of elements representing the continuous and disperse phases were used.

At relatively low thermoplastic (TP) contents (10% and below) in the polycyanate network, there was no doubt that the dicyanate component formed the only continuous phase while the thermoplastic component was dispersed in the continuous phase. The DMA and microscopic results suggested that most of the thermosetting polycyanate component formed the major continuous phase, while a small fraction of the dicyanate component was precipitated along with the thermoplastic component, which together formed the minor dispersed phase.

To quantitatively describe the component distribution in these two phases, a mechanical model was fitted with the storage modulus data. Figure 1 shows a comparison between the experimental storage modulus data of the BEDCy/PSu-90/10 blend with the calculated values according to the Takayanagi model [13], :

$$E = (1 - \lambda)E_A + \lambda / [(1 - \phi) / E_A + \phi / E_U] \quad (1)$$

where λ is the volume fraction of the discontinuous phase consisting of both components A and U; $1 - \lambda$ is the volume fraction of the continuous phase; ϕ is the volume fraction of the thermoplastic (U) component in the discontinuous phase. A good fit to this model infers a simple continuous-dispersed morphology for the blend and the parameters obtained from the model may be used to determine the relative compositions in the phases. The best fitting was obtained with parameters $\lambda = 0.125$, and $\phi = 0.80$. The values of the parameters for the BEDCy/PSu (90/10) blend suggest that the BEDCy component forms the only continuous phase domain, which accounts for 87.5 vol% of the blend, and that the remaining 12.5 vol% is occupied by the dispersed phase domain consisting of primarily the thermoplastic polysulfone (80 vol% of the disperse phase) and a much smaller fraction of the BEDCy component (20%).

Fig. 1. Log modulus vs. temperature for the BEDCy/PSu-90/10 blend.

The experimental data are compared with the prediction according to the Takayanagi model with $\lambda = 0.125$, $\phi = 0.80$.

Additional Continuous Phase. The DMA and microscopy data suggested that as the thermoplastic (TP) contents were increased beyond 10 vol% in the blends, the dispersed phase domain gradually increased in sizes while the thermosetting BEDCy continuous phase domain began to recede. In addition, the thermoplastic component also gradually formed another continuous phase that co-existed with the retreating BEDCy continuous phase. At this time, the thermosetting BEDCy was not the only dominant continuous phase in the BEDCy/PSu blend any more. For the BEDCy/PSu blend, the Takayanagi equation was found to be no longer valid for describing this now quite complex morphology and its effect on the mechanical properties of the blends required a completely different approach of interpretation. A new model was employed to describe the complex morphology that might include dual continuous phases with a dispersed phase consisting of changing compositions of the thermoplastic and thermosetting components. This was done by properly taking into account that a certain volume fraction of the thermoplastic component was excluded from the dispersed phase and formed another continuous phase, which constituted a dual continuity along with the original thermosetting BEDCy continuous phase (A). Equation (1) is modified by adding a parallel element (E_U) and a parameter ξ to the Takayanagi model to represent the modulus and volume fraction, respectively, of this new continuous phase:

$$E = (1 - \lambda - \xi)E_A + \lambda / [(1 - \phi) / E_A + \phi / E_U] + \xi E_U \quad (2)$$

where ξ is the volume fraction of the thermoplastic (U) component that forms a co-continuous phase domain along with the continuous thermoset phase domain (A).

The fitness of this new model is shown in the blend system with higher thermoplastic contents. Figure 2 shows the experimental storage modulus data of the BEDCy/PSu (80/20) blend in comparison with the calculated values according to the new model as discussed above.

Fig. 2. Log modulus vs. temperature for the BEDCy/PSu-80/20 blend.

The experimental data are compared with the calculated values according to the Parallel-Series-Parallel model with $\lambda = 0.30$, $\phi = 0.33$, and $\xi = 0.10$.

In contrast with the dispersed phase domain of the BEDCy-90/PSu-10 blend where the dispersed phase is of primarily thermoplastic nature, the dispersed phase domain of the BEDCy-80/PSu-20 blend now consists of a reduced composition of the thermoplastic polysulfone (33 vol%) and a larger fraction of the BEDCy component (67%).

Morphology Changes during Cure: Example of Blends of PEI with an epoxy

Phase separation remained throughout the cure process, however, the phase domains and the dimensions underwent significant changes as the cure progressed. The phase morphology of the blend samples of three compositions (10, 30, and 50 phr) were monitored by scanning electron microscopy as a function of time of cure conducted at the temperature of 177 °C. Morphology development of the blends at the other two temperatures was found to be similar. Figure 3 shows the SEM micrographs of the epoxy/PEI(10 phr) blend samples cured for 5, 25, and 120 minutes of cure time, respectively, at 177 °C. Micrograph 3-a shows that, initially, the PEI-rich phase domain was relatively large (10-20 μm) and distinctly separated from the surrounding epoxy-rich domain at 5 minutes of cure time. Micrograph 3-b shows that at 25 min of cure time, the PEI-rich phase domain was then gradually broken into smaller particulate discrete domains, further finely separated by the reacting/crosslinking epoxy component originally dissolved in the PEI-rich domain. Micrograph. 3-d shows that at the end of cure (120 min),

the PEI-rich domain clearly exists as fine dispersed particles ($< 1 \mu\text{m}$) surrounded by the only continuous epoxy phase domain.

Fig. 3 SEM for epoxy/PEI(10 phr) blend samples cured for different time at 177°C . (a): $t = 5 \text{ min.}$, $\alpha_1 = 6.1 \%$; (b): $t = 25 \text{ min.}$, $\alpha_1 = 29.8 \%$; (c): $t = 34 \text{ min.}$, $\alpha_1 = 46.3 \%$; (d): $t = 120 \text{ min.}$, $\alpha_1 = 84.3 \%$.

To summarize, the morphology of the blends not only changed as a function of cure time, but also was affected by the blend compositions. Figure 4 shows a series of schematic diagrams of morphology development for the epoxy/PEI blends at different cure states as well as different compositions, with the y-axis as the blend composition, and the x-axis as the time of cure.

Fig. 4 Schematic morphology evolution for epoxy/PEI blends at various cure states and/or blend compositions.

These schematic diagrams show that the morphology of the blends were all similar at low levels of conversion. As the cure time is increased and thus the levels of conversion becomes higher, the epoxy blend of 10 phr PEI or lower develops a morphology with the epoxy-rich phase forming the only continuous domain. The epoxy blends of 50 phr PEI or higher, however, eventually develop a morphology of two continuous intertwined meshes, with one being the continuous epoxy domain and the other being the continuous PEI domain. For the blends of intermediate compositions, the fractured surface exhibits a mixed pattern of these two distinct morphologies.

CONCLUSION

The binary blends of the thermosetting BEDCy with the thermoplastic(s), such as polysulfone or polyetherimide, exhibited an interesting phase-separated morphology, whose continuity and phase compositions were dependent on compositions. A new Parallel-Series-Parallel mechanical model constructed by adding an additional parallel element to the Takayanagi model was applied to quantitatively fit with the modulus data of the binary blends.

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